

Risk for Violence Screening in the Emergency Department

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Background

- Violence in the healthcare setting has surged post-pandemic
- 8/10 nurses report at least 1 incidence of WPV in the past year
- Recent requirements by the Joint Commission call for better education and training by hospitals to decrease WPV
- The highest risk of violence is seen in EDs & ED nurses are 4X more likely to face violence than nurses in other units
- Various violence assessment screening tools have been developed to decrease violent episodes, but few have been validated for use in the ED

Problem Statement

- In a southern California hospital, the number of physical assaults on ED nurses increased by approximately 25%, in the last few years
- The current protocol with a screening tool needed to be updated

Purpose Statement

- The aim of this quality improvement project was to revise, implement, & evaluate the hospital's violence prevention protocol using a new, validated, evidence-based screening tool

PDSA Framework

Methods

- **Design:** Quality improvement project
- **Setting:** Triage unit in ED of a 453-bed tertiary care public teaching hospital in Los Angeles, CA
- **Participants:** 100 RNs who work in the Triage Unit of the ED
- **Measures:** QOVPRAO screening tool, demographic survey, CCPAI, surveillance data

Los Angeles County Department of Health Services
VIOLENCE PREVENTION SCREENING
Queensland Occupational Violence Patient Risk Assessment Tool (QOVPRAO)

Does the patient have any of the following:

RISK DOMAINS	QUALIFYING CHARACTERISTICS	RESPONSES
Aggression history	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Known history of aggression • Alert for aggressive behavior 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No = 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Behavioral concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Angry • Clenched fist • Demanding • Resisting care • Threatening language • Other concerning behaviors 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No = 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Clinical presentation of concern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alcohol intoxication • Drug intoxication • Erratic or irrational cognition 	Presence/Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Absence/No = 0 <input type="checkbox"/>
Scoring	Low Moderate High	Yes = 0 <input type="checkbox"/> Yes = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Yes = 2-3 <input type="checkbox"/>

Interventions and Safety Precautions

Low risk (score = 0)	Moderate risk (score = 1)	High risk (score = 2-3)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain a safe distance of at least one leg length away • Communicate in a calm, concise, and clear manner • Inform the patient that they are in a safe environment • Explain all procedures/interventions to patient/family • Provide timely information to address patient concerns • Perform periodic rounding per unit protocol • Never allow a patient to come between you and the exit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow all low-risk interventions AND: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiate Property for Violent Behavior care protocol • Activate Golden Hand procedures (per institution) • Use a two-person approach • Remove any hazardous items/unnecessary medical equipment • Set clear limits and boundaries on acceptable behavior and provide positive feedback • Use less restrictive interventions such as but not limited to de-escalation and verbal redirection • Collaborate with the patient and interdisciplinary team to find appropriate interventions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow all low and moderate-risk interventions AND: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get help to manage patient safety • Consider activating Code Gold if the patient is exhibiting violent behavior • Consider moving the patient to a safe area room if possible

Results

Screening Tool Compliance

- 3857 patients were screened using the QOVPRAO (50% completion)
- Risk for violence scores: low (97%), moderate (1%), and <1% high risk over a 6-week period
- No reported staff assaults occurred during the pilot period

Participant Demographics

- 51% of nurses had 5 years of ED experience, were 25-34 years old (39%), female (76%), and were BSN educated (75%)

Screening Tool Feedback

- 59% of triage nurses reported that the QOVPRAO adequately identified patients at risk for violence
- 43% reported that the tool was easy to complete and quickly assessed risk
- 54% preferred to have the QOVPRAO tool replace previous tools

CCPAI Results

- There were no significant changes in the levels of confidence in interacting with aggressive patients pre- and post-implementation (p=0.0476)
- Male nurses were significantly more confident than female nurses

Limitations

- Tool completion and adherence to the protocol was low at 50%, which may have been due to relocation of the triage unit during implementation
- In addition, the tool was only available as a paper and pencil instrument and not on the EMR
- The training that took place only involved training nurses in completing the screening tool & reviewing the current protocol

Recommendations

- Use of the QOVPRAO was well received and should be incorporated into the EMR
- More targeted training is needed to increase RN confidence in managing assaultive behavior
- To include the QOVPRAO as part of the onboarding documentation training

Implications

- Further intervention is needed given the lack of RN confidence in dealing with aggressive patients in the ED
- The QOVPRAO will be expanded to other units & in other partnering DHS hospitals
- The use of a validated screening tool is only the first step in the establishment of an effective violence prevention program

References

